

A combination of cis-2-decenoic acid and antibiotics eradicates pre-established catheter-associated biofilms

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Abstract

The catheterized urinary tract provides ideal conditions for the development of biofilm populations. Catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTIs) are recalcitrant to existing antimicrobial treatments; therefore, established biofilms are not eradicated completely after treatment and surviving biofilm cells will carry on the infection. *Cis*-2-decenoic acid (CDA), an unsaturated fatty acid, is capable of inhibiting biofilm formation by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and of inducing the dispersion of established biofilms by multiple types of micro-organisms. Here, the ability of CDA to induce dispersal in pre-established single- and dual-species biofilms formed by *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was measured by using both semi-batch and continuous cultures bioassays. Removal of the biofilms by combined CDA and antibiotics (ciprofloxacin or ampicillin) was evaluated using microtitre plate assays (crystal violet staining). The c.f.u. counts were determined to assess the potential of combined CDA treatments to kill and eradicate pre-established biofilms formed on catheters. The effects of combined CDA treatments on biofilm surface area and bacteria viability were evaluated using fluorescence microscopy, digital image analysis and live/dead staining. To investigate the ability of CDA to prevent biofilm formation, single and mixed cultures were grown in the presence

and absence of CDA. Treatment of pre-established biofilms with only 310 nM CDA resulted in at least threefold increase in the number of planktonic cells in all cultures tested. Whilst none of the antibiotics alone exerted a significant effect on c.f.u. counts and percentage of surface area covered by the biofilms, combined CDA treatments led to at least a 78% reduction in biofilm biomass in all cases. Moreover, most of the biofilm cells remaining on the surface were killed by antibiotics. The addition of 310 nM CDA significantly prevented biofilm formation by the tested micro-organisms, even within mixed cultures, indicating the ability of CDA to inhibit biofilm formation by other types of bacteria in addition to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These findings suggested that the biofilm-preventive characteristics of CDA make it a noble candidate for inhibition of biofilm-associated infections such as CAUTIs, which paves the way toward developing new strategies to control biofilms in clinical as well as industrial settings.

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